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PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING TECHNICAL TOOLS FOR GROWING AND HARVESTING POTATOES

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Abstract

The cultivation and harvesting of potatoes is traditionally based on single-machine units, which is accompanied by multiple passes of equipment across the field, an increase in material and labor costs. The article presents the development prospects for the development of multifunctional units with a combined mounted and multi-threaded use of engine power. Due to the use of combined units, increased functionality of individual machines that are part of these units, the labor costs of machine operators, field workers in the main and auxiliary operations, as well as the consumption of fuel and lubricants, are significantly reduced.

Keywords. Potato growing, tiller, potato digger, energy intensity, resource-saving, front mounted machines, combined units.

The potato is the fourth largest food in the world after wheat, corn and rice. As a valuable source of high-quality protein, vitamins, minerals and carbohydrates, potatoes are one of the main food of plant origin for humans in some countries.

Growing and harvesting potatoes is an important part of the agricultural industry of the Republic for providing the population of the Republic with potatoes of its own production, while much attention is paid to the development of a complex of modern highly efficient and resource-saving technical means that ensure the cultivation and digging of potatoes with minimal energy consumption. The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 outlines “...further strengthening of the country's food security, expanding the production of environmentally friendly products, a significant increase in the export potential of the agricultural sector; optimization of areas for growing potatoes and other vegetable crops by reducing land plots intended for cotton and wheat. To accomplish these tasks, it is necessary to develop a set of machines for growing and harvesting potatoes, which ensures the required quality of work in the soil and climatic conditions of our Republic

with minimal energy consumption, this will reduce imports due to the localization of production, which is one of the important tasks [1].

The pace of development of potato growing should make it possible to fully meet the needs of the population for this product. Currently, the production of potatoes in farms is characterized by high labor costs, monetary and material resources. This is explained by the absence of certain types of machines, and the existing technologies for cultivating and harvesting potatoes are traditionally based on single machine units, which is accompanied by multiple passes of heavy equipment across the field, an increase in material and labor costs and agrotechnical terms of work.

The solution to the problem of reducing labor and resource costs is possible by modernizing existing standard technologies for growing potatoes and using specialized multifunctional multi-machine units in potato growing that perform two or more technological operations in one pass through the field, using a number of new machines that improve the efficiency of the industry.

Based on the results of the analysis of patent information materials of foreign experience, it was found

that multifunctional units with a combined hitch and multi-threaded use of engine power are used in almost all agricultural sectors in the preparation of fodder in animal husbandry, in tillage, in the cultivation and harvesting of potatoes and other crops. The reason that does not allow to completion the combined multifunctional units is the low energy saturation. Particularly acute is the lack of energy resources that meet the specific requirements of the cultivation of vegetable crops and potatoes.

Thanks to the financial resources allocated for research and development work, according to the parameters and initial requirements of NIIMSX and NIIOBiK in SKB Tractor was created on the basis of a serial cotton-growing tractor TTZ 80.11, OJSC TTZ, a tractor under the brand name TTZ-100 SP, a tractor that satisfies requirements for use as part of multifunctional combined units [2]. Vegetable tractor of traction class 1.4 with a power of 77 kW, wheel scheme 4×4, front and rear wheel track 1400 mm, wide speed range, rear and front hydraulic systems with a load capacity of up to 20 kN, as well as front and rear selection shafts power, sufficient agrotechnical clearance make it possible to effectively aggregate combined multifunctional multi-machine units.

Specialists of NIIMSX, NIIOBiK together with BMKB-Agromash OAO developed experimental models of front-mounted machines: a soil mill with horizontal active working bodies, a boom sprayer and tops of the chopper, as well as rear-mounted machines: a reversible plow for smooth plowing, a row vegetable cultivator with energy-saving workers organs, potato planters and potato diggers.

At present, combined units have been created and are undergoing economic tests, which, without prejudice to the agrotechnical and technological quality of work, can be combined in one pass across the field [3]:

- grinding of plant residues from the previous crop with a frontal tops-stem grinder and simultaneous plowing of the soil with a rear-mounted reversible plow;
- surface loosening of the soil with a frontal soil mill and simultaneous planting of potatoes with a rear-mounted potato planter;
- the cultivation of row spacing of vegetable crops and simultaneous treatment of plants with pesticides to control pests and diseases with a frontal boom-sprayer;
- harvesting potato tops with a frontal tops-stem grinder and simultaneous digging of tubers onto the field surface with a rear-mounted potato digger.

When cultivating late potatoes, the main tillage is carried out by one combined unit, consisting of a chopper of plant residues and a reversible plow, in one pass across the field. The crop residue chopper is mounted

on the front hitch and the reversible plow is on the rear hitch of the tractor.

After plowing with a reversible plow, breaking furrows and tailing ridges are not formed, therefore, work to eliminate the flaws that are inevitable in traditional plowing is excluded. Potato planting is carried out by a combined unit, which in one pass performs pre-plant tillage by loosening to a depth of 15 cm, planting potato tubers and forming ridges. During this period, two-time chiseling of the soil to a depth of 14-15 cm and thinning are excluded from the traditional set of fieldwork.

The use of a milling cultivator as part of a combined planting unit, according to experts, allows, when growing potatoes, to ensure the creation of the most favorable environment around the developing tuber.

In the most responsible and time-consuming period of care for potato plantings, the main task is to maintain optimal conditions for the growth and formation of tubers throughout the growing season. Even a one-time violation of air or water regimes leads to irreversible changes in the structure of tuber tissues and the inevitable loss of yield.

The developed combined tilled unit consists of a front-mounted universal sprayer and a universal rear-mounted cultivator-fertilizer allows:

- destroy weeds, break up soil clods, keep the soil between the rows in a loose state, cut furrows for irrigation, apply mineral fertilizers or mixtures of organic-mineral fertilizers to the soil;
- to produce the formation of full-profile ridges over rows of tubers up to 22-25 cm high, providing a loose structure inside and compacted side slopes, which is important for creating favorable conditions for the growth and development of potato plants and the accumulation of tubers;
- in any combination with the above operations, simultaneously spray crops with chemical and biological preparations and weeds and soil with herbicides.

Entering the potato fields of combined aggregates, which make it possible to carry out a wide variety of combinations of agricultural practices in one pass across the field, will not only reduce the number of passes along the aisles of heavy equipment but, most importantly, will significantly increase efficiency if it is necessary to carry out urgent treatments that cannot wait.

The combined potato harvester allows you to combine two operations - topping with a front-mounted chopper and digging up potato tubers with a rear-mounted harvester with crop spreading over the field surface.

A modernized KK-2 potato digger was developed for harvesting potatoes (picture).

a) front view; b) rear view; 1 - support-lump-destroying device; 2 - main section shares; 3 - intermediate plowshare; 4 - wavy ripper; 5 – swather Pic 1. Modernized potato digger KK-2

During the working stroke across the field, the supporting-clod-destroying device 1 crushes strong lumps of potato beds and loosens their upper part and slopes, sectional shares 2 digs in two rows of potatoes and direct the tuberous layer to the separating rod elevator 3 to separate small soil impurities and partially tops from the tubers. Wavy rippers 4 installed on the separator contribute to the completeness of separation. From the bar separator, tubers with vegetable impurities and large clods of soil enter the lattice cascade of the swather 5 for further separation from impurities, then the tubers are dumped onto the field surface, and

the tapering lattices contribute to the formation of a narrow swath of tubers, which are then picked up by hand.

This combination of work in one unit significantly reduces the time of harvesting and improves the quality of the food product.

We have also developed a KSN-2 potato digger-loader, which provides crushing of strong, large lumps of potato beds and loosening the soil above the elevator, as well as removing incoming tops and unloading potato tubers onto a vehicle with minimal damage [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

1-support-lump-destroying devise with elastic rods; 2-plowshare; 3- elevator; 4-accumulative asset elevator; Pic.2. Technological scheme of the KSN-2 potato digger-sorter

When harvesting potatoes, the developed potato digger-sorter KSN-2 is designed to ensure the quality of work and minimum energy consumption. Therefore, the KTP-2 potato digger-sorter offered by us during the digging process ensures minimal loss and damage to potato tubers, as well as reduces labor costs and increases productivity.

The transferred part of the potato bed to elevator 3 is loosened and then fed to the cone-shaped sorter 4. The tops are removed by the sorter 4, the soil is loosened and the potato tubers are fed to the ground along the grates of the sorter.

The cone sorter reduces tuber fall rates and as a result, reduces damage to potato tubers.

The advantage of the KSN-2 potato digger-sorter compared to serial machines (KTN-2V, KST-1.4) consists in the fact that a clod-destroying device is installed in front of the plowshare and the overall dimensions are smaller, as well as a sorter is installed for extinguishing and falling speed of tubers, as well as simultaneously sorting potato tubers. This helps to reduce traction resistance, and rub, damage to tubers.

Findings

1. Preliminary comparative assessment of the main indicators of traditional and recommended to significantly reduce the number of passes of machine-tractor units over the row spacing of vegetable crops and potatoes during the season.

2. Based on the estimated potato sowing area of 10 hectares, per season, working according to the recommended technologies, it is possible to reduce the labor costs of machine operators when cultivating and harvesting potatoes by 45%.

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